

From Bullying to Thriving: A Qualitative Study on Resilience in College Students with a History of Childhood Bullying

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Childhood bullying constitutes a major psychosocial stressor with long-term consequences for psychological functioning that often extend into emerging adulthood. Despite the risk factors, some individuals show resilience and manage to thrive. Exploring and strengthening protective factors helps individuals reduce or prevent the harmful impacts associated with those risks. The present study explores the protective factors contributing to resilience in college students with a childhood bullying experience. Individual in-depth interviews were conducted with semi-structured interviews on 24 college students (12 males & 12 females) aged 18-25 with a childhood history of bullying from a mid-sized city in South India. The data was analysed using inductive thematic analysis. The results revealed that social support, activity-based coping, cognitive and emotional regulation, and self-efficacy emerged as protective factors. Protective factors play a crucial role in fostering resilience and well-being among this population. Future research should focus on emphasizing the necessity of early detection of bullying experiences and highlighting the importance of targeted psychosocial interventions to enhance resilience and reduce distress among emerging adults with such bullying histories.

Keywords: Childhood bullying, protective factors, emerging adults, resilience

Childhood bullying is a common type of peer victimization, characterized by repeated aggression and power imbalance, and has been consistently associated with negative psychological outcomes (Olweus, 1993). Initial experiences of bullying can disrupt the development of social confidence and trust, hindering victims from establishing significant peer relationships in adulthood (Jantzer et al., 2006). Studies in developmental and clinical psychology show that these impacts go beyond emotional distress in childhood or adolescence, frequently having lasting effects on emotional and psychological functioning (Copeland et al., 2013). Bullying experienced in high school negatively affects motivation and the adjustment to college, a time that demands independence, resilience, and social adaptability (Goodboy et al., 2015). Bullying experienced during the school years can have long-lasting effects, frequently extending into adulthood and causing challenges with mental health and establishing or sustaining social relationships (Arseneault, 2018).

Victims of bullying have poor mental health functioning, negative perceptions of well-being and increased symptoms of depression and anxiety, and worse physical health in comparison to individuals who have not experienced bullying (Holt et al., 2014). Teacher humiliation was identified as a positive predictor of externalizing

problems in adolescents (Annalakshmi & Deepak, 2021). These consequences are mainly prominent in the context of the transition to college, where first-year students who have faced bullying experiences report higher rates of depression and anxiety than their peers (Bowes et al., 2015; Copeland et al., 2013). Bullying behaviours and victimization were negatively associated with adolescents' resilience and self-efficacy, emphasizing the significance of resilience as an important psychological resource in contexts of peer aggression (Narayanan & Betts, 2014). Individuals with higher resilience are likely to experience less negative impact from adverse events, mostly due to better coping mechanisms, emotion regulation skills, and access to supportive relationships (Sapouna & Wolke, 2013).

In a bullying context, the constant victimization may produce a feeling of hopelessness, enhancing the impression of the victim that he or she can do nothing with, or stop the victimization. This perceived entrapment increases emotional strain and adds to the increased psychological distress (Eskin et al., 2007). Emerging adulthood as a developmental period when the identity is explored, the need to manage emotions grows, the psychological sensitivity increases, the instability is seen in relationships, work, and personal beliefs, and the close focus on self-reflection and self-determination is all the primary factors that make the developmental stage of emerging adulthood very crucial in terms of understanding how previous experience, including bullying, affects further well-being and is especially influential in shaping the current psychological condition of an individual (Arnett, 2000).

The victims of bullying might be enrolling in college with reduced self-efficacy and increased anxiety that may affect their involvement in college academics and social activities. Both past and current victims report a much lower level of autonomy, competence, and motivation, which are among the central psychological needs in terms of academic achievement and personal

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Development (Young-Jones et al., 2014). Resilience plays an important role in diminishing the long-term psychological consequences of bullying by enabling individuals to cope positively despite the adversity (Chukwuemeka et al., 2025). These studies show that bullying during the formative years of schooling can be challenging in terms of emotional stability, peer integration and long-term psychological well-being of college students. Resilience helps students manage challenges more effectively and is associated with improved academic performance by assisting them in overcoming hurdles and utilizing social support (Annalakshmi, 2010). Instead of being a personality trait or a genetic trait, resilience is developed through repeated positive experiences as well as relationships with family members, peers, neighbours, and the community at large (Brooks, 2006; Rutter, 2006). Students who possess high levels of resilience are able to cope more effectively with difficulties and experience less psychological distress, even in demanding situations (Mabrouk et al., 2022). In the context of bullying victimization and emerging adulthood, resilience acts as an interactive process between social resources and personal agency within the environment (Lidberg et al., 2024).

Enhancing resilience has been suggested as a strategy to reduce the impact of victimization because not all children who are bullied have psychosocial adjustment issues (Bowes et al., 2010). Resilience arises from individual, family, and peer factors which help to lower depression and delinquency in adolescents who have been exposed to bullying (Sapouna & Wolke, 2013). Resilience acts as a protective factor that reduces the risk of targeting and protecting the emotional consequences in case of victimization (Hinduja & Patchin, 2017). However, its effectiveness may vary depending on the severity of victimization, emphasizing the importance of early intervention and support to strengthen resilience through different developmental stages. Therefore, the present qualitative study's objective is to understand the factors that support resilience in undergraduate college students with an experience of childhood bullying.

Method

Participants

A sample of 400 undergraduate students with a history of childhood bullying completed a survey that comprised a measure of resilience for a larger study. 24 participants who demonstrated high levels of resilience were chosen and interviewed, the results of which are presented in this paper. The participants were 12 males and 12 females recruited from four colleges in a mid-sized city in South India. All participants were in the age group of 18-25 ($M= 19.54$, $SD=1.25$).

Ethical Protocol

The present research was conducted in terms of ethical guidelines

proposed by the American Psychological Association (APA). Institutional approval was acquired from colleges selected for the research. The research was initiated in compliance with the proposal that was approved by the doctoral committee. Bharathiar University Human Ethics Committee (BUHEC/95/2024, dated: 18.12.2024) approval was also obtained. Before conducting the interviews, all participants were informed of the purpose of the interview, the criteria on which they were selected, and assured about the confidentiality and privacy of the information provided and made aware of their right to decline or withdraw from the study at any time. They were assured that the collected data would be used only for research purposes. Written informed consent was acquired from the participants before conducting the interview. All the semi-structured interviews were audio-recorded, and the audio recordings were stored in the laptop of the researcher, which was secured with a password.

Measure

A semi-structured interview schedule was developed to discover the protective factors of college students with a history of childhood bullying. The questions were focused on exploring personal experiences, coping strategies, and sources of support of the participants. One-on-one interviews were held with participants in a secure and private environment in their respective colleges. The semi-structured interview schedule included questions addressing the nature and context of bullying experiences; emotional and affective responses at the time of the incident; short and long-term psychological and behavioral impacts; and the coping mechanisms and resilience factors employed by the individuals. All questions were framed as open-ended items, allowing respondents to elaborate freely.

Procedure

Interview sessions were recorded using audio devices, and the recordings were safely stored on a password-secured laptop of the researcher. All ethical guidelines, such as maintaining confidentiality and informed consent from the participants were strictly followed throughout the process. The recorded interview content in the Malayalam language was transcribed into English and then analyzed using thematic analysis to examine the factors that contribute to the resilience of the college students who had a history of being bullied in childhood.

Data Analysis

Inductive thematic analysis technique grounded on Braun and Clarke's (2006) framework was used to analyze the interview data. Thematic analysis is a flexible approach that enables the generation of rich, detailed, and in-depth insights from qualitative data.

Results

Main Theme	Sub-themes	Codes
Social support	Family support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Emotional reassurance from family ● Parental concern and validation
	Peer support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Friendships offering emotional support ● Consistent peer support
	Teacher support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Guidance and understanding from teachers ● Faculty maintained a non-judgmental atmosphere

Activity-based Coping	Physical activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in sports (cricket, swimming, tennis, badminton) • Engagement in martial arts and karate • Meditation and mindfulness exercises • Practice of yoga • Regular exercise or gym workouts • Outdoor activities such as walking or cycling
	Recreational activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drawing and painting for relaxation • Reading and writing for calming and self-expression • Music engagement (listening, singing, or playing instruments) • Craftwork or creative projects • Gardening as a calming and restorative activity
Cognitive and emotion regulation	Positive reappraisal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interpreting bullying as a reflection of others' insecurities • Using positive self-talk to reinforce confidence • Shifting perspective to view challenges as opportunities for growth
	Emotional intelligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultivating emotional awareness to recognize and process feelings effectively • Expressing emotions in healthy ways
Self-efficacy	Boundary setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speaking up assertively when confronted with bullying or unfair treatment • Choosing to disengage from peer groups that encourage harmful behaviors • Defining clear limits in friendships to protect personal well-being
	Adaptability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to adjust to the situation • Prioritizing self-care to maintain well-being
	Trust in self &	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-confidence to overcome difficult times
	Hopefulness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depending on oneself to manage bullying

Discussion

Four key broad themes of protective factors were identified: (i) social support, (ii) activity-based coping, (iii) cognitive and emotional regulation, and (iv) self-efficacy.

Social Support: One of the themes that emerged from the interview is social support, which includes three sub-themes: family support, peer support and teacher support. Social support has been demonstrated to be a protective element for children and adolescents when exposed to harmful experiences, including bullying, because it helps to reduce the probability of victimization and diminishes its negative effects. Social support can come from various sources, including parents, educators, peers, and schoolmates as psychological or physical support (Rueger et al., 2008). Adolescents who go through peer aggression at school gain significant advantages when they receive strong support from their parents (Oriol et al., 2017). Increased support from parents and peers has been linked to a reduced risk of being bullied (Biswas et al., 2020; Graber et al., 2006). Teachers offering social support to students demonstrate their concern for students' emotional needs and welfare, which primarily adds to students' feelings of connection at school (Hallinan, 2008).

"I had a very supportive family with whom I was able to share my problems. Also, I had good understanding friends who supported me every time." (#P1)

In addition to family support, participants also spoke of the valuable role that the support given by peers and teachers played in enabling them to deal with the bullying experiences. These support systems played a part in emotional reassurance, a sense of belonging, and practical assistance that was provided in the school and social setting.

"I acknowledge that true friends and a few supportive teachers were crucial in my life; they helped me in my studies and

influenced me to keep moving forward." (#P24)

Activity-based coping. One of the themes that emerged from the analysis is activity-based coping, comprising two sub-themes: physical activities and recreational activities. Participants described activities (e.g., sports, martial arts, exercise, yoga) and leisure activities (e.g., painting, music) as methods of coping with stress and restoring a feeling of control and reducing the emotional impact of bullying. Youth who are physically inactive may face a higher chance of being bullied because of inadequate motor skills (Barnett et al., 2008) and physical fitness (Garcia-Hermoso et al., 2019) suggesting that regular physical activity may be protective by strengthening competence and confidence. In line with this, physical activity is discussed as a promotive factor for adolescent mental health, supporting emotion regulation and social adjustment (Sibold et al., 2015) which aligns with participants' use of sports/exercise as activity-based coping. Students who participated in athletics had a lower likelihood of experiencing verbal victimization (Sheridan et al., 2022). Overall, regular participation in physical activity can be interpreted as an activity-based coping resource that strengthens motor competence and physical fitness, making one less vulnerable to bullying and reducing its psychological impact.

In the case of middle adolescents, engaging in extracurricular activities was associated with reduced victimization, and it is possible that sports and other activities might serve as protective factors that minimize bullying behavior and the chance of victimization (Hong et al., 2022). Also, many students enjoy the act of painting to convey their emotions. During painting, students have the opportunity to freely express their emotions and ideas through art and have been demonstrated to assist students in comprehending bullying more efficiently by reflecting on their personal experiences (Crawford, 2011). Participants emphasized how sustained engagement in activities fostered discipline, confidence, and a shift toward personal strengths.

"I used to practice martial arts and karate consistently. Because of my consistent practice and focus, now I don't have to wear spectacles. This has improved my eyesight. I think that consistency was a starting point in my life. I started to focus more on my strengths." (#P14)

In addition to physical activities, participants also emphasized recreational activities and creative activities as important resources for coping. The activities (drawing, painting, reading, writing, music, craftwork, & gardening) appeared to facilitate relaxation, expression of emotions and create a feeling of restoration.

"I often turned to painting when I was stressed. Putting colors on canvas was a way to express emotions I couldn't put into words." (#P7)

Cognitive and Emotion Regulation. One of the themes that emerged from the interview is cognitive and emotion regulation, which includes two sub-themes: positive reappraisal and emotional intelligence. Reframing the meaning of bullying by positive reappraisal changes reactions from negative to more positive and increases resilience (John & Gross, 2004). Positive reappraisal has been recognized as an effective coping strategy in decreasing depressive symptoms among adolescents exposed to bullying (De Camargo & Rice, 2020). In bullying-victimization cases, higher positive reappraisal decreases the link between bullying-victimization and symptoms of anxiety (Garnefski & Kraaij, 2014).

Emotion regulation and inspiration increase resilience as they are associated with positive emotions, which are not compatible with negative emotions (Solomon & Corbit, 1974). These processes empower an individual to identify internal and external resources and put them to their best use to overcome the challenges by increasing the immediate range of thoughts and actions (Fredrickson, 2001). Emotional intelligence serves as a protective component against being a victim of school bullying (Fernández-Berrocal & Aranda, 2017). Students with stronger emotion regulation abilities and understanding were less likely to experience school bullying as victims (León-Del-Barco et al., 2020).

"I started to think why the opposite person is doing this and I realized that may be to cover up their inferiority complex, they are doing this. To an extent, I would say bullying is for personal growth but when it exceeds the limit, it can ruin a life. These situations made me realize who I am. I have more strength than I believe." (#P22)

Self-efficacy. One of the themes that emerged from the analysis is self-efficacy, comprising three sub-themes: boundary setting, adaptability, and trust in self and hopefulness. The conceptualization of self-efficacy as a protective factor in bullying may be supported by an intervention study, which found that greater self-efficacy among adolescents is linked with an improved health-related quality of life irrespective of bullying victimization and perpetration experiences (Haraldstad et al., 2019). Evidence from an intervention study supports the awareness of conceptualizing self-efficacy as a modifiable protective resource that can strengthen coping and well-being in vulnerable children (Kvarme et al., 2010) aligning with the broader theme of self-efficacy as a protective factor in the context of bullying.

Assertiveness skills allow one to speak up responsibly and at the same time avoid being bullied repeatedly (Herman et al., 2020). The number of bullying cases among adolescents tends to reduce after assertiveness-based therapy (Sadeli & Karneli, 2022). Assertiveness

therapy helps the victims to boost their self-confidence and increase their ability to share their emotions openly and honestly (Weinstein et al., 2011). Assertiveness training improves adolescents' awareness of their right to safeguard themselves against bullying behaviors from others. Assertive people establish good relationships with others, protect themselves against maltreatment, express both positive and negative ideas *without stress, guilt, anxiety or invading on others' rights* (Eslami et al., 2015).

"I stayed away from people who made things harder and spent time with friends who made me feel safe. If someone crossed the line, I spoke up or walked away instead of keeping quiet. I understood that we should speak for ourselves. I kept making small changes to feel better and reminded myself that things wouldn't stay bad forever." (#P11)

Conclusion

The present study highlights the insights into the protective factors that influence resilience in undergraduate students who experienced childhood bullying. Considering the protective factors that emerged, such as social support, activity-based coping, cognitive and emotional regulation, and self-efficacy, the present research contributes to the understanding of the critical resources that may foster resilience and improve the overall well-being of the participants with experiences of childhood bullying. The findings of the current study also demonstrate that resilience is not only a personal internal strength, but it is also an interactive process occurring between an individual and the social supports in their environment, thus emphasizing the importance of addressing both personal qualities and the environmental context. The study's findings highlight the importance of policy and intervention being focused on promoting protective factors that enhance the resilience of students and eventually contributing to better psychological and emotional well-being. The long-lasting impacts of early peer victimization may be solved by including interventions of resilience-building in student counseling services.

Limitations and Implications of the Study

Although the study addressed crucial research areas, it is necessary to acknowledge some noteworthy limitations. The participants were exclusively selected from a single city. Including samples from other cities may improve the generalizability of the findings to a broader population. In the present study, the risk factors were not explored. Participants' accounts may be affected by social desirability and recall bias.

The results have practical implications for school and family-based prevention and intervention of bullying. The protective factors suggest that responses to bullying must be directed not only at preventing incidents but also at enhancing the supports that help students cope and recover. Schools must be proactive in building relationship-based protection through facilitating credible teacher support, peer-based support, and family involvement. Access to structured, supervised activities (sports, arts, & recreation clubs) could also be increased, as low-stigma coping spaces, through which a sense of belonging, routine, and emotional healing can be achieved in programmes. The planning of prevention must provide systems-level measures to increase supervision in high-risk educational environments, provide safe reporting mechanisms, and regular referral to supportive mental health services to make sure that

protective resources are available constantly, rather than after severe incidents.

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